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VIOLENT CONFLICTS AND POVERTY RATE IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: The growing tension in Nigeria as a result of violent conflicts has reached a worrisome height and has taken an unprecedented dimension that has never been imagined by experts in the field of national security. This study focused on the nexus between violent conflicts and the poverty rate in Nigeria from 2000 to 2024. The specific objectives of this study were to evaluate the impact of violent conflicts on the achievement of the Millenium Development Goal 1 and to establish the threat that violent conflicts pose to the achievement of Nigeria's Sustainable Development Goal 1. This study used time series data while adopting an ex-post facto research design. The study used the descriptive statistical analysis method of data analysis, which involves the numerical measurement of variables. Thus, the datasets generated from the documentary observation were presented in tables, graphs, and charts and were analyzed. The results revealed that violent conflicts in Nigeria destroyed lives and properties, economic infrastructure, and restricted people from engaging meaningfully in agriculture, trade, and other economic activities, which stimulated poverty. These outcomes undermined people's well-being and thus disrupted the achievement of MDG 1. With only 4 years left to the end of SDGs and with the persistence of violent conflicts, the study foresees difficulty in attaining SDG 1. Consequently, the study recommended that the government and other development partners should adopt conflict resolution, peacebuilding and peacekeeping as elements of poverty reduction or alleviation policy or program, particularly with respect to achieving SDG 1.

Keywords: Violent Conflicts, Poverty Rate, MDG 1, SDG 1, Nigeria.

1. Introduction

In recent times, the increasing interdependence and interaction between countries and the centrality of the security, survival, and wellbeing of the people in these interactions, as well as the negative impacts of underdevelopment on the countries all over the world, have made development a shared concern globally. Consequently, there have been many global programs tackle the world's development problems. Within this framework, two outstanding global development program initiatives were lauched: - the Millennium

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Development Goals (MDGs) (2000-2015), and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (2015-2030) (Morton, Pencheon & Spuires, 2017).

The MDGs include eradicating extreme poverty and hunger, achieving universal primary education, promoting gender equality and women empowerment, reducing child mortality, improving maternal health, combating HIV/AIDS, malaria, and other diseases, ensuring environmental sustainability, and developing a global partnership for education (Morton, et al., 2017).

The UN General Assembly approved the United Nations Millennium Development Declaration during its Millennium Summit in September 2000 (Morton, et al., 2017). The Declaration, which urged worldwide collaboration to end extreme poverty, was the first global policy with quantifiable goals to be accepted by all UN member states and the world's top development organizations. Given the implications of poverty on nations, MDG 1 was 'Eradication of Extreme Poverty'. The deadline for achieving the MDG targets was 2015, a 15-year time frame. Unfortunately, Nigeria failed to meet MDG 1 at the expiration of this time frame (Local Governments for Sustainability [ICLEI], 2015).

During the 70th session of the UN General Assembly on September 25–27, 2015, a special summit of UN member states was convened to endorse the post-2015 development agenda. At the conclusion of this remarkable conference, the declaration "Transforming Our World - the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development" was approved (UN, 2015). It was an unparalleled worldwide appeal for wealth, harmony, and cooperation for individuals, the environment, and humanity. The 2030 Agenda includes 169 specific targets and indicators in addition to a set of 17 globally relevant, integrated sustainable development objectives to promote collaborative transformative action on a global scale. These objectives are officially known as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Morton et al., 2017; UN, 2015).

The 17 global goals are as follows: (1) No poverty; (2) Zero hunger; (3) Good health and well-being; (4) Equal education; (5) Gender equality; (6) Clean water and sanitation; (7) Affordable and clean energy; (8) Decent work and economic growth; (9) Industry, innovation, and infrastructure; (10) Reduced inequalities; (11) Sustainable cities and communities; (12) Responsible consumption and production; (13) Climate action; (14) Life below water; (15) Life on land; (16) Peace, justice and institutions and (17) Partnership for the goals (UN, 2015; Morton, et al., 2017).

The first goal and objective, otherwise referred to as MDG 1 was to reduce extreme poverty in all its forms. The SDGs preserve the MDGs' focus on eradicating poverty, which is its first goal and objective, referred to as SDG1, but it also took a more comprehensive approach to global development and preserving human life on earth (ICLEI, 2015).

The literature has dominantly blamed Nigeria's future to meet MDG 1 on a lack of proper funding, lack of political will, corruption, lack of adequate data and statistics, inadequate policy implementation, and other factors, (Ibietan & Ekhosuehi, 2013; Ekundayo, 2015; Godbless et al, 2019). While this study agrees with the foregoing, it varies and argues that the role of conflict has been overlooked. It is trite to state here that every region of the Nigerian state is bedeviled with one form of violent conflict or the other (Amiara & Omeje, 2019; Adeleke, 2020). These range from the Niger Delta conflicts, Boko Haram insurgency, herders-farmers conflicts, secessionist agitations, and banditry to other ethnic and religious conflicts around the country (Badejogbin, 2013; Oli, et al., 2018; Orakwue, 2019; Shaka, 2019; European Asylum Support Office [EASO] 2021). Ignoring the impact of conflicts in the analysis of why the country failed to achieve MDG 1 misses a point that appears to put SDG 1 at risk.

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Poverty is undoubtedly a bane to the development and well-being of people and has far reaching implications for nations. Sequel to this fact, the eradication of extreme poverty is both an MDG 1 and an SDG 1 (ICLEI, 2015). It is a truism that Nigeria lost out on achieving MDG 1. The SDGs have been ongoing for over 9 years now, with Nigeria showing no good prospects of achieving SDG 1. It stands to reason that if not addressed, the factors that undermined the achievement of MDG 1 will invariably undermine SDG 1.

Scholars have blamed Nigeria's inability to achieve MDG1 on several factors. These include climate change and environmental degradation, lack of proper funding, lack of political will, corruption, lack of adequate data and statistics, and inadequate policy implementation, (Ibietan & Ekhosuehi, 2013; Ekundayo, 2015; Godbless, et al., 2019; Ikechukwu & Emeto, 2019), ignoring the role of conflicts. In some cases, conflicts are driven by poverty; other cases, conflicts induce poverty. In other words, conflict and poverty have a symbiotic relationship (Draman, 2003; cited in Uzoh, 2016). The point here is that conflicts weaken the conditions necessary for growth.

Violent conflicts undermine the social and economic infrastructure that is already in place and decrease the level of living standards. Funds that might otherwise be allocated for additional development projects are instead used to finance war or to rebuild infrastructure and habitats damaged by conflicts. Conflicts make individuals impoverished or worsen their poverty status by draining society's economy. When society's economy is drained, majority of states and their governments are unable to provide the basic needs of the public. Conflicts destroy lives, property, social amenities and socio-economic infrastructure (Okonkwo et al., 2015). The inference is that when people lose their possessions, they become impoverished. People will become less productive if socioeconomic activities are disrupted. This is because they will not be able to continue with their productive businesses. Individuals lose access to necessary products and services when socioeconomic infrastructure is destroyed (Ikejiaku, 2009). This study examines the role of conflicts in undermining the achievement of MDG 1 and the threat it poses to achieving SDG 1 in Nigeria.

Specifically, this study seeks to achieve the following: (i) examine how violent conflicts undermine the achievement of MDG 1 in Nigeria, and (ii) establish the threat conflicts pose to the achievement of SDG 1 in Nigeria.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Concept of Violent Conflict

To understand violent conflicts, it is necessary to briefly define conflict. Conflict is an intrinsic and inevitable aspect of human life. According to Francis (2004), conflict is the pursuit of incompatible interests and goals by different parties or groups. Violent conflict refers to the use of force and arms in the pursuit of incompatible and particular interest and goals.

The potential for conflicts exists whenever and wherever people come into contact; the probability of conflicts greatly increases as people are organized into groups to pursue a common goal. When a conflict escalates into open warfare and results in at least 25 battle-related fatalities annually, it is considered violent. Armed or violent conflict occurs when there is opposition to one's own armed group or between governments (intra-state), or when there is an armed conflict between states (Uzoh, 2016).

Conflict involves disagreement, contention, and the pursuit of incompatible interest between different parties through violent or non-violent means. It means the clash of opposing interests and the struggle of each interest group to actualize its interests which is often violent. As such, "conflict" refers to armed violent attacks on people,

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property, infrastructure, or territories, violent clashes, and other violent activities that cause threat, injury, and harm to lives, property, and social and economic infrastructure. It also involves armed confrontation between groups.

2.1.2 The concept of poverty

The term poverty has elicited a plethora of definitions. Poverty implies a state of deprivation and lack of security in basic human needs (Agboola & Emmanuel, 2008; Ibaba, 2012). It is measured with purchasing power parity (PPP), food intake, Human Development Index (HDI), Gender-related Development Index (GDI), Gender Empowerment Measures (GEM) and Human Poverty Index (HDI). However, PPP is the most commonly used measure and considers an individual to be poor if he/she earns less than \$1.00 - \$2.00 per day. Insufficient income, which undermines the security of basic goods and services (food, health care, education, shelter), inability to produce for themselves, inability to meet basic nutritional needs, and low consumption and expenditure are considered to be the basic characteristics of the poor (Olaniyan & Bankole, 2005; cited in Ibaba, 2012).

Poverty is both a cultural construct and a universal reality. Bjorn (2002) created five poverty categories based on the type and degree of poverty. Absolute poverty is a state of deprivation brought on by a small income or by not having access to necessities such as food, clean water, sanitary conditions, health care, housing, education, and knowledge. The second category is relative poverty, which is defined from a comparative perspective. In this definition, poverty is not absolute but rather relative and is based on the opinions of individuals within a given society regarding what constitutes a reasonable and acceptable standard of living and lifestyle in accordance with prevailing customs. The third category is administrative poverty, which encompasses all individuals who qualify for state assistance because of their inability to generate revenue or temporary unemployment. Consensual poverty is based on what the public believes to be subsistence living. The fifth is contextual poverty, which is determined by comparing poverty to a certain community's socioeconomic and cultural norms.

Adejumobi (2006) stated that there are three aspects of poverty to consider. First, it is a multifaceted structural issue that presents itself in the political, social, and economic spheres. Second, poverty is a process. Poverty is neither a particular occurrence nor a natural state of events. It often happens when some factors work together to compromise a person's ability and standard of living. The third aspect is its relative character; it is subject to cultural relativism. The problem of poverty has socio-cultural variances in addition to universal norms. Some communities may not view something as indicative of poverty.

Each of these poverty categories has a common denominator. The point that poverty is a universal state of deprivation and want that pushes its victims to the margins of society is emphasized by all of them. In sum, poverty entails a lack of capacity and access to survival, and existential and emotional needs.

2.1.3 Millennium Development Goals

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) are a set of nine goals that were targeted to be achieved in 2015, which emerged from the meeting of the United Nations (UN) in, 2000 referred to as the Millennium Summit, which was held in the United States of America (USA). The MDGs include the following (1) eradication of extreme poverty and hunger; (2) achievement of universal primary education; (3) promotion of gender equality and empowerment of women; (4) reduction of child mortality; (5) improvement of maternal health; (6) combating HIV/AIDS, malaria, and other diseases; (7) ensuring environmental sustainability; and (8) development of a

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global partnership for education (Morton, et al., 2017). Notwithstanding, this study only considers MDG 1 – Eradication of extreme poverty and hunger.

2.1.4 Sustainable Development Goal

To guarantee worldwide sustainable development by 2030, the United Nations, in collaboration with the different governments and agencies of its member nations, established a set of 17 well defined global goals known as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). These were the results of the United Nations Millennium Declaration, adopted by the UN General Assembly at its September 2000 Millennium Summit (Morton et al., 2017). Among the 17 global objectives are: (1) No poverty: By 2030, eradicate extreme poverty in all its manifestations; (2) Zero hunger: Put an end to hunger, secure food, enhance nutrition, and advance sustainable agriculture; (3) Good health and wellbeing: Make sure that everyone, regardless of age, has a healthy life; (4) Equal education: guarantee inclusive, equitable, high-quality education and encourage opportunities for lifelong learning for everyone; (5) Gender equality: attain gender equality and empower women and girls; (6) Clean water and sanitation: guarantee access to and sustainable management of water and sanitation for everyone; (7) Affordable and clean energy: Ensure that everyone has access to affordable, dependable, sustainable, and modern energy; (8) Decent work and economic growth: Encourage full and productive employment, sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth; (9) Industry, innovation, and infrastructure: Construct resilient infrastructure, encourage inclusive and sustainable industrialisation, and foster innovation; (10) Decreased inequality: lessen disparities both inside and across nations; (11) Sustainable communities and cities: Create inclusive, secure, resilient, and sustainable human settlements; (12) Responsible consumption and production: Make sure that patterns of consumption and production are sustainable; (13) Climate action: Take immediate action to mitigate the effects of climate change; (14) Life below water: Conserve and use the oceans, seas, and marine resources for sustainable development; (15) Life on land: Preserve, restore, and promote the sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems; (16) Peace, Justice, and Institutions: Encourage societies that are inclusive and peaceful for sustainable development, provide everyone access to justice, and create institutions that are inclusive, efficient, and responsible for everyone; and (17) Partnership for the goals: Strengthen the means of implementation and revitalize global partnership for sustainable development (ICLEI, 2015; UN, 2015). However, this study focuses on SDG 1 – No poverty: End extreme poverty in all forms by 2030.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Frustration - Aggression Theory

The frustration-aggression theory, first developed by John Dollard (1939) and later expanded and modified by Leonard Berkowitz (1962) and Aubrey Yates (1962), occupies the most common place among social conflict theories as the explanation for violent behaviour stemming from the inability to fulfill needs. This theory relies on psychological theories of motivation and behaviour as well as frustration and aggression (Anifowose, 1982). In an attempt to explain aggression, scholars point to the difference between what people feel they want or deserve and what they actually get, that is, the want-get-ratio (Feierabend, 1969) and the difference between expected and actual need satisfaction (Davies, 1962). Where expected does not meet attainment, people tend to confront those they hold responsible for frustrating their ambitions. This is the central argument in Gurr's relative deprivation thesis (1970) which says that, 'the greater the discrepancy, however marginal, between what is sought and what seem attainable, the greater will be the chances that anger and violence will result. The main premise of frustration-aggression theory is that aggression is not just undertaken as a neutral reaction or instinct but is the

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outcome of frustration. In a situation where the legitimate desires of an individual or group are denied either directly or indirectly by the way the society is structured, the feeling of disappointment to the expression of anger through violence that will be directed at those the individual or group holds responsible or people who are directly or indirectly related to them.

Justification of the Theory

The theory of frustration - aggression is appropriate to our study as it captures the issue of violent conflicts in Nigeria vis-à-vis its socio-production and reproduction configurations and their overall interaction with achieving not only development but also the MDG 1 and SDG 1. “Eradication of Extreme Poverty, the MDG 1 and the SDG 1 have a central goal of ensuring the continuous attainment of humankind’s basic need – security and survival as advanced by the theory. It is pertinent to note that development has various definitions, perspectives, and dimensions. Notwithstanding, the development literature agrees that development is not a project but a process, a continuous effort and achievement of man’s survival needs. It is within this process that all the development efforts of the Nigerian State can be located, ranging from national development plans and other policies as well as adoption of the MDGs and SDGs can be located, ranging from national development plans and other policies as well as adoption of the MDGs and the SDGs.

It is also within the frustration-aggression matrix that the various conflicts in Nigeria can be located. Drawing from frustration-aggression argument, it is within this matrix that different interest groups are formed, dissatisfied groups are identified and different conflicts ensue among and between the people. These conflagrations are born out of perceived or real attempts by different groups to express their dissatisfaction. The Niger Delta conflicts primarily between the indigenous people, the Nigerian Federal Government and the multinational oil companies (MNOCs) and between and among the people; the herders-farmers conflicts, the ethnic and religious conflicts in Kaduna State and other parts of northern Nigeria, and the secessionist agitation in the southeast geopolitical zone and other parts of the country are a few examples of such conflicts. Interestingly, the contradiction in this state of affairs is that the violent conflicts further become a problem to the people’s ability to achieve and sustain their survival needs cum development as it further creates conditions of insecurity and threat to survival. This is because the very processes and resources required for security and survival are disrupted or destroyed, thereby undermining wealth creation and development and creating poverty.

The implication here is that the dominant conflicts in Nigeria occur in the people’s endeavour to meet their survival needs. Whether or not these endeavours are carried out fairly or unfairly is important as it is also an intervening variable in the conflict situation. What is more important is the threat to the survival of a people which will, no doubt ignite violent conflicts. Therefore, it is sacrosanct that government and other development partners make efforts, policies and programs to capture these realities and address them in the formulation and implementation of these policies and programs if their goals and objectives must be achieved.

2.3 Empirical Literature Review

This study’s empirical literature is reviewed to cover two perspectives that are considered pertinent to this research and the Nigerian situation. These include the conflict and security and economic system perspectives. Accordingly, they are reviewed as follows:

2.3.1 Conflict and the Security Perspective

Certain scholars indicted conflicts and insecurity in Nigeria as the cause of failure or poor performance of development and poverty reduction policies and programs (Ewetan & Urhie, 2014; Onime, 2018; Ndubuisi-Okolo

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& Anigbuogu, 2019). Scholars that espouse the insecurity perspective have linked the failure of development in Nigeria to the country's inherent conflicts and insurity challenges. The central argument of this perspective is that over the years, insecurity has hindered the country's development (Ewetan & Urhie, 2014; Onime, 2018; Ndubuisi-Okolo & Anigbuogu, 2019). Specifically, Ewetan and Urhie (2014) argued that the spate of insecurity in the country has been increasing and consequently poses grave threat to lives and property, hinders business activities, and discourages local and foreign investment.

Ndubuisi-Okolo and Anigbuogu (2019) interrogated the theme of insecurity and industrialization. Their study found that insecurity in Nigeria is a significant factor that hinders the country's industrialization and sustainable development. On the basis of this finding, their study concluded that effective industrialization growth and sustainable development are only possible in Nigeria when the insecurity issue is addressed.

The studies of Ewetan and Urhie (2014), Onime (2028) and Ndubuisi-Okolo and Anigbuogu (2019) have linked insecurity to the state of poor development in Nigeria but have ignored the basic cause of insecurity in the country. Insecurity is not a stand-alone factor but a major fallout of conflicts. As such, insecurity cannot be adequately discussed and addressed without considering conflicts.

However, other studies have examined conflicts, the basic cause of insecurity in Nigeria, and linked it to the country's development impediments. Adekoya (2010) argued that the bulk of Nigeria's development resources are derived from oil revenue. However, the Niger Delta region from which oil is extracted faces grave environmental challenges as a result of poor environmental management in the exploration process. Thus, the environmental challenges in the region serve as a key driver of conflicts in the region, which are impediments to Nigeria's transition to a green economy. Ibaba (2011; 2017) took a more comprehensive approach in his discussion of peacebuilding in the Niger Delta, demonstrating the link between conflicts and development in the Niger Delta and Nigeria at large. Interestingly, Ibaba (2011) noted that while the neglect of development is partly the cause of conflicts in the region, conflicts also serve as impediments to development in the region and the Nigerian State as oil production, which funds a huge chunk of the country's budget, is adversely reduced. This was the basic reason for the Niger Delta Presidential Amnesty program (PAP). Among other factors, Ibaba (2011; 2017) noted the crisis of leadership in the region and the resultant poor quality of governance, service delivery, open corruption, and the consequent neglect of development as drivers of conflicts in the region.

2.3.2 Economic System Perspective

Another perspective put forward by scholars is that the structure and nature of the Nigerian economic system is not very amenable to the success of development and poverty reduction policies and programs. Scholars that support this perspective locate Nigeria's development problem in the structure of the country's economic system (Robinson & Anthony, 2014; Onyeyekwere, 2016). Thus, Robinson and Anthony (2014) argue that Nigeria's externally oriented mono-economic foundation is a significant element that has undermined the nation's developmental aspirations. To the detriment of other resources, the nation's survival is primarily dependent on crude oil. The disarticulated, externally oriented and reliant structure of developing economies is the basis upon which other characteristics appear to be built.

Lawal and Oluwatoyin (2017) pointed out that Nigeria's mono-economic foundation is a significant impediment to the country's development initiatives. They claim that the nation mostly relies on crude oil to survive at the expense of other resources. The other sectors of the economy are all disregarded. For example, the agricultural sector, which supported the Nigerian economy throughout the 1950s and 1960s, has been marginalized over time.

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When there is almost nothing to sell, how could the government promote exports? Sustainable development is not attainable because of the lack of economic diversification (Lawal & Oluwatoyin, 2017).

Scholars also observed that the problems associated with starting and sustaining businesses in the Nigerian economic system account for impediments on economic growth and development (Onyekwere (2016) observed that the challenges faced by businesses and entrepreneurs, such as bureaucratic red tape, exorbitant fees, and corrupt public servants, impede business expansion and economic progress in Nigeria.

Apart from the enduring issue of energy, Nigeria's administrations have consistently neglected to provide the necessary support to the indigenous industry. For example, Lucas (2015) contends that since the discovery of crude oil, successive governments have ignored other economic sectors. Agriculture is a sector that is overlooked. Approximately 70% of Nigerians found employment in the agricultural sector, which also produced foreign exchange earnings and a market for industrial sector products. Lucas (2015) claims that agriculture fed the country's expanding population and supplied the industry with enough new materials to expand.

Literature Gap

It is discernable from the foregoing literature review that a good percentage of the literature focused on Nigeria's development problem and its inherent causes, such as the country's economic system, corruption, and poor development planning. A relatively small part of the literature focused on the role of insecurity but did not pay adequate attention to the more important issue of conflicts, which is the major driver of insecurity. While a few studies interrogated the issue of conflicts and linked it to development problems in Nigeria, they focused on the Niger Delta region of the country, with a focus on oil exploration related conflicts and their interplay with the development of the region and by extension, the country.

The literature lacks a holistic approach to the impact of conflicts on the development of a country and its development plans. The literature has not empirically linked the impacts of conflicts to Nigeria's failure to address the problem of poverty as captured in MDG 1 and how to prevent loopholes on attaining SDG 1. Although the literature captured the conditions under which the MDGs were implemented that led to its failure still exist and may serve as a bane to the SDGs as well, the role of conflict was not captured. How conflicts played a major role in the failure of MDG 1, the threat it presents to SDG 1, and the inherent lessons are yet to be adequately investigated in the literature. This study attempts to fill this gap.

3. Materials and Methods

This study adopted an ex-post facto research design. The design is appropriate for studies with historical or periodic measurement of the phenomenon of interest, and particularly where the researcher is not in a position to influence or manipulate the investigation's outcome. Thus, the ex-post facto design is appropriate for this study as the relationship that exists between conflict and poverty, particularly the MDG 1 and SDG 1 in Nigeria, has been examined over the years. Accordingly, time series data were used in this study. The time series data of the ex-post facto research design removes the potential for fast generalization and manages the validity risks associated with research methods such as the one-shot case study design.

The following are the functional relations for the time-series design

$$PR = f(X_i) \quad (1)$$

Where:

PR = poverty rate and dependent variable

X_i = set of explanatory variables

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Equation 1 is further expanded to include:

$$PR = f(\text{IFVC}, \text{VCOE}, \text{PMDGs}, \text{GRE}, \text{GCE}, \text{NEGS})$$

Where:

IFVC = Incidences and Fatality of Violent Conflicts

VEC = Violent Education Conflict

PMDGs = performance of millennium development goals

GRE = Government recurrent expenditure

GCE = Government capital expenditure

This study examines the trajectory of minimal achievement of MDG1 and SDG 1 over a period of twenty-five (25) years (2000-2024) locating it in the context of inherent conflicts in the country and lessons derivable from MDG 1. The justification of this timeframe is that the Millennium Development Goals came into effect in 2000, elapsed in 2015, and the Sustainable Development Goals came into effect in 2015. Therefore, we attribute the failure to achieve MDG 1 and the threat to the achievement of SDG 1 to conflicts in the country. The threat to achieving SDG 1 is also attributed to the failure to learn the inherent lessons from the failure of MDG 1.

3.2 Data Collection

This study employed the documentary observation method of data collection. Consequently, the study adopted the secondary method of data collection. Data were gathered from secondary sources, such as official and organizational publications and databases, journal articles and other academic publications, news media, and the internet. Types of data collected in the study include violent incidences and fatalities; types of violent conflicts and perpetrators; performance of the MDGs; poverty rates; property destroyed by violent incidences; IDPs, impact of violent conflicts on education; government expenditure on security and military; government recurrent expenditure; government capital expenditure; and Nigeria exports of goods and services.

Data on poverty rates were collected from the NBS (2024), World Bank (2025) *World Development Report: Conflict, Security and Development*, and World Bank (2024) World Development Indicators. Data on the incidences and fatalities of violent conflicts were collected from the Armed Conflict Location and Event Data database, Global Terrorism Index report, European Asylum Support Office (2025) report, Human Rights Watch (2013) report, International Crisis Group (2022) and (2024) reports, newspaper reports, and Adigun (2022) study. Data on the impact of violent conflicts on education were collected from the Global Coalition to Protect Education from Attack (GCPEA, 2018) report. Data on the performance of the MDGs were collected from the Nigerian MDG Report (2015) and the National Bureau of Statistics (2015) Millennium Development Goals Performance Tracking Survey Report. Data on government recurrent expenditure, government capital expenditure, and Nigeria exports of goods and services from Statistical bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria.

3.3 Method of Data Analysis

The incidence of violent conflicts and poverty rates are numerically measurable. Therefore, the descriptive statistical analysis method of data analysis, which involves the numerical measurement of variables, was utilized. Thus, the dataset generated from the documentary observation were presented in tables, graphs, and charts and analyzed where applicable.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Conflicts and Failure of MDG 1 in Nigeria

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This section addresses the first research objective raised in the first section of the study. This study begins by exploring the inherent conflict situation and the manifestations of violence in Nigeria from 2000 to 2024. It then examined the theoretical and empirical link between conflicts and poverty (MDG 1 and SDG 1). Furthermore, a brief discussion of Nigeria's performance of MDG 1 was examined. Then, the specific role of conflict in the failure of MDG 1 in Nigeria is explored. This is followed by highlighting salient lessons from the role of conflicts in Nigeria's failure to achieve MDG 1 and how the same can serve as a blueprint for the implementation and achievement of SDG 1.

4.1.1 Anatomy of Conflicts and Violence Architecture in Nigeria (2000-2023)

The eradication or alleviation of poverty to the barest minimum across the globe, which are the common objectives of SDG 1 and MDG 1, is a fundamental element that necessitates social organization (Morton, et al., 2017). Interestingly, politics is the fulcrum of every social organization. Evidently, every social organization seeks to achieve and enhance the conditions necessary for life processes that are sacrosanct to security and survival. This involves the production and reproduction of human needs. The production and reproduction of human needs cannot be achieved solitary, thus, making it a social enterprise (Ogban-Iyam, 1991). In essence, the need for commodious resource production and allocation necessitates society. However, human nature creates a condition for conflicts in the resource production and allocation process. Being selfish and greedy, humans tend to produce and allocate resources to themselves at the expense of others (Ibaba, 2010).

Politics is the means through which these conflicts are resolved. Political theorists and scholars have theorized different individual perspectives on the best means of social organization (Mukherjee & Ramaswamy, 2007). Despite the various conceptualisations of politics, the resolution of conflicts vis-à-vis resource production and distribution run through them. Therefore, when David Easton (1965) defined politics as the authoritative allocation of resources in a society, and Harold Lasswell (1930) defined it as the determination of who gets what, when, and how, they indicate a process by which resources are produced and distributed authoritatively backed by power, creating order (Ibaba, 2010).

The foregoing indicates that politics is ubiquitous, as it exists in every association, such as the family, school, social organization, religious, private corporations, and the state. Nevertheless, its association with the state stands out and is the domain of political literature and discourse.

Evidently, the Nigerian state is yet to sufficiently organize its resources production and distribution matrix to contain the conflicts that emanate from the process. Consequently, the country has a deplorable history of protracted conflicts, which further undermines the smooth production and distribution of resources to cushion poverty. The period between 2000 and 2024 has recorded some of the country's worst forms of conflicts. In fact, every state in each of the six geopolitical zones of the country has witnessed one or the other form of violent conflict (EASO, 2021). The manifestation of violent conflicts during this period took complex and multidimensional forms. These include, inter alia, organized crime related violence, insurgencies, terrorism, political violence, ethnic, religious, and communal clashes and secessionist agitations (EASO, 2021; Nigeria Watch, 2007). However, certain violent conflicts in this period stand out in relation to their impact on SDG 1 and MDG 1; thus, they require special attention. These include the Niger Delta insurgency, the Boko Haram conundrum, the herders-farmers conflicts, criminal violence and banditry, and secessionist agitations.

Table 4.1 Principal Perpetrators of Violence

Variables	Newspaper	Total
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		The Punch	The Guardian	Vanguard	
Herders	Freq (%)	89(53)	109(57.4)	173(52.6)	371(54)
Farmers	Freq (%)	4(2.4)	1(0.5)	1(0.3)	6(0.9)
Others	Freq (%)	5(3)	4(2.1)	6(1.8)	15(2.2)
Not clear	Freq (%)	70(41.7)	76(40)	149(45.3)	295(42.9)
Total	Freq (%)	168(100)	190(100)	329(100)	687(100)

Source: Olomjobi and Ajilore (2018, 44)

Table 4.1 clearly demonstrates that herders are viewed and documented as the main perpetrators of violence in Nigeria’s herder-farmers feud. Specifically, The Punch indicated that the frequency of violence by herders is 89, representing 53%, while that by farmers are four (4), representing 2.4%. The Guardian indicated that the frequency of violence by herders is 109, representing 57.4%, whereas that by famers is one (1), representing 0.5%. Vanguard indicated that the frequency of violence by herders is 173, representing 52.6%, while famers is one (1), representing 0.3%. This is further demonstrated in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: Chart on Principal Perpetrators of Violence in Herders-Farmers Conflicts

Source: Adapted from Olomjobi and Ajilore (2018, 44)

The existence of stern strife between herders and farmers has resulted in numerous clashes, attacks, and counterattacks that have resulted in the loss of thousands of lives, displacement of many more, and destruction of property worth billions of Naira. According to the Global Terrorism Index (2015), the number of deaths linked to herders’ militancy in several states of Nigeria increased from 80 in 2012 to 1,229 in 2014. According to a 2013 Human Rights Watch report, between 2010 and 2013, 3,000 people died as a result of fighting between farmers and herders in Nigeria’s north-central area between 2010 and 2013. Similarly, on February 24, 2016, around 300 people were killed in a raid by Fulani herders in the Benue State community of Agatu (Obeya, 2019). In addition to murder, herders have also been involved in rape and kidnapping (Lawal et al., 2015).

Herdsmen raided a section of Southern Kaduna in December 2015, kidnaping 880 people, destroying 53 communities, burning 1,422 houses, 18 churches, and one elementary school. In 2016, herdsmen attacked the

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Uzo Uwani hamlet in Enugu State in 2016, killing over 40 people and destroying property. According to General Abdulsalami Abubakar, the conflicts cost \$13.7 billion, displaced 62,000 people, murdered 2,500 people, and cost the impacted states 47% of their domestic revenue in 2016 alone (Agbese, 2017). The Christian Solidarity Network (CSN) documented that in the first quarter of 2018, the Fulani militia claimed the lives of 1,061 people in 106 attacks on communities in the states of Adamawa, Benue, southern Kaduna, Kogi, Nasarawa, Plateau, and Taraba; additional 17 people were killed in attacks in the country's south (Akinloye, 2018). The Implication here is that farm and cattle, which serve as the economic liver wire of herders and farmers, are destroyed on a large scale. Innocent residents of host communities also frequently become victims of conflicts between farmers and herders (Yusuf, 2019).

Herdsmen have been classified as a terror group and called the fourth most lethal terror group in the world due to the severity of their illicit actions in recent years (GTI, 2015). It has been projected that the hostilities between 2015 and 2018 resulted in at least 3 641 deaths and an estimated 300,000 displaced people (Amnesty International [AI], 2018a). The Middle Belt of Nigeria is the focal point of farmer-herder disputes, which have spread to the Southwest and southeast Regions as additional grazing space is sought after. Benue, Plateau, Taraba, Adamawa, Kaduna, Kwara, Borno, and Zamfara are the most severely impacted areas (EASO, 2021).

Reports regarding the number of people killed in the battle between farmers and herders are frequently contradictory. However, every information that is currently available indicates that the amount of violence and casualties that have been reported thus far have increased exponentially. These range from the number of fatalities to the number displaced persons to the value of property and agricultural produce destroyed, which result in increasing poverty and consequently, undermine the achievement of MDG 1 and SDG 1.

4.1.2 Violent Conflicts and Poverty Rate (MDG 1 and SDG 1): Assessing the Impact

A clear understanding of the link between violent conflicts and poverty is pertinent to facilitate comprehension of the discourse on the role played by conflicts in undermining the achievement of MDG 1 and the threat it poses to SDG 1 in Nigeria. This would be better appreciated by understanding the concept and context of poverty, its causes and how violent conflicts engender and promote the contexts and causes of poverty. This section first demonstrates the concept, context, and causes of poverty. Then, with the application of both theoretical and empirical evidence, the study examines how violent conflicts engender and enhance the contexts of poverty.

While opinions vary about its precise definition, poverty is universally understood as a state or condition marked by a lack of basic necessities such as clothing, food, shelter, healthcare, clean water, and basic education.

The link between violent conflicts and poverty can be demonstrated theoretically and empirically. Two theories dominate the academic literature on the impact of violent conflicts on poverty. From an economic perspective, conflicts result in casualties, fatalities, missed opportunities, and education. If left unchecked, human capital might not quickly rebuild resulting in persistent poverty. On the social front, alienation and exclusion may also result in a class that has no interest in peace, and the effects of conflict may cause psychological damage and aggressiveness (Annan et al., 2011).

Several factors can obstruct economic growth, leading to persistently high poverty rates. Violent conflicts stand out as a major factor that can obstruct economic growth and increase poverty rates. Conflicts can have a negative impact on labour, health, and economic outcomes. Conflict can negatively impact household welfare and impose costs on both individuals and the economy through a number of wide pathways Odozi & Oyelere, 2019).

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The foregoing indicates that violent conflicts engender critical conditions that impact people’s access to both market and non-market goods and services. This simultaneously creates poverty for some and hinders others from escaping poverty. Violent conflicts not only inhibit the improvement of living conditions but, also deteriorate them in most cases. Empirical evidence corroborates this argument, as it suggests that nations devoid of armed conflicts are progressively emerging from poverty (World Bank, 2011). In contrast, poverty is concentrated in nations with civil conflicts, ethnic conflicts, or organized crime (The Economist, 2011).

4.1.3 MDG 1 Performance: Examining Nigeria’s Failure to Meet MDG 1

According to the Presidential Committee on MDGs, Nigeria must meet the targets for the MDGs by dropping the country’s poverty rate from 42.7% in 1990 to 21.35% in 2015 (Durokifa & Abdul-Wasi, 2016). However, poverty status in the country fluctuated in the period with progress or retrogression, which was estimated to be 42.7% as measured using the 1992 statistics. Nigeria saw an increase in poverty from 53.3% in 2004 to 65.6% in 2006, after which it began to decline to 54.4% in 2011 (Nigerian Millennium Development Goal Report, 2015). Nonetheless, a 2014 World Bank estimate from 2014 indicated that 33.1% of Nigerians are impoverished, which is more in line with the 2015 target of 21.35% for 2015 (Durokifa & Abdul-Wasi, 2016). A more comprehensive and chronological index of poverty covering the period 2000 – 2015 is provided by the NBS Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.2: Poverty Indices in Nigeria 2000-2015

Source: (Ozigbu, 2018)

Figure 4.2 shows that Nigeria’s poverty rate increased between 2000 and 2015. Nigeria had an average population percentage of 69.01% living in poverty. Additionally, the graphic shows that more than half of the population was impoverished during all except 2014 of the time. In 2002, the percentage of people living below the poverty line reached a peak in 2002, accounting for 88% of the population.

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The figures of poverty rate in Nigeria with regard to the MDG 1 period as put forward by different organization are somewhat conflicting. However, the single thread that runs through all of them is the fact that no notable improvement in the poverty rate of Nigeria was observed from the beginning to the end of the MDG 1 era as envisioned by the target. As such, the country lost out on meeting MDG 1, as commonly indicated in the figures. Taking a leaf from the NBS indices, more than half of the population still wallowed in a state of lack and want in basic human needs such as food, shelter, clothing, clean water, education, and health as well as the inability or lack of the means of securing the necessities of life.

4.1.4 Conflicts and the Failure of MDG 1 in Nigeria

As mentioned elsewhere, the objective of both MDG 1 and SDG 1 is to alleviate poverty to a minimum. However, poverty is not a standalone factor that can be eradicated in isolation. There must be an interplay of certain variables for people to move from a state of lack and inability to meet basic needs and necessities of life to a state of having and the capacity to meet them. The common denominator for this process is production. Goods and services must be produced, exchanged, and consumed and wealth must be created to sustain the capacity to meet basic human needs. The production process only made possible by certain resources and processes. Marxian Political Economy analyses demonstrate that labour power, objects of labour and instruments of labour, collectively referred to as the productive forces are the basic determiners of society’s productivity.

Here, labour power is the individual capacity to practically perform a productive activity that is dependent on knowledge and physical strength. Therefore, it follows that education, training, and health stand out as labour power enhancers. The point here is that an educated, knowledgeable, experienced, and healthy population is a requirement for any society to meet its needs and eradicate poverty. Thus, anything that undermines an educated, knowledgeable, experienced, and healthy population invariably induces poverty and contributes to Nigeria’s failure of MDG 1 and threat to SDG 1

Notably, the Niger Delta conflicts and the Boko Haram conundrum were not the only conflict situations during the MDG 1 implementation period. While they melted out the most significant violence in the country at the said period, other forms of less significant conflicts were also in vogue and contributed to violence incidents that impacted negatively on the MDG 1 through livelihood disruption. This is because they all contributed to the loss of lives, disruption of socioeconomic activities, and destruction of property and social infrastructure. Figure 4.2. Highlight of different types of violent incidents and fatalities in a particular period.

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Figure 4.3: Types of Violent Incident's and Fatalities in Nigeria 2001-2015

Source: ACLED (2024)

As indicated in Figure 4.2., violent incidents include violence against civilians, which had 2515 incidents and 29869 fatalities; battles, which 2088 incidents and 18183 fatalities; explosion/remote violence, which had 474 incidents and 5817 fatalities; riots, which had 827 incidents and 3343 fatalities, strategic development, which had 201 and 53 fatalities; and protests, which had 1741 incidents and 52 fatalities.

Figure 4.4: Recurrent expenditure as a proportion of total recurrent expenditure (%)

Source: Ikpe (2017, pp. 390)

The amount spent on defense and internal security increased from approximately 13% to 20% between 2009 and 2012, then fell to 15% in 2013 before rising again until 2015. The increasing trend is consistent with traditional projections for security expenditure.

Figure 4.5: Capital expenditure as a proportion of total capital expenditure (%)

Source: Ikpe (2017, pp. 390)

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Arguments regarding government investment, best illustrated by capital expenditure in Figure 4.5, are related to the crowding effect of higher security spending. It shows that spending on defense and security increased by roughly 3% to 10% in 2010, then it saw a minor decrease between 2010 and 2011, and it continued to rise again thenceforth. In comparison, between 2009 and 2015, public spending decreased in manufacturing, transportation, communications, mining, and agriculture, as well as in the productive sectors. Decreases in capital spending for communications, transportation, and agriculture outpace decline in recurrent expenditure. This bolsters Gupta et al., budgetary modifications will result in decreased investment. The shift in public spending from investments in the economy to military and security, along with possible declines in consumption and adverse effects on production, has an additional economic impact.

Figure 4.6: Exports of Goods and Services as a percentage of GDP

Source: Ikpe (2017, pp. 393)

It is anticipated that violent conflicts will cause trade indicators to become unstable, with export growth and volume being the most affected. The fundamental causes of this result include the redirection of resources toward security requirements, the disruption of labour and production operations, and the resulting reduction in export supply (Stewart, 1993). Nigeria’s export performance has been deteriorating, and this trend has actually worsened since the intensification of the crisis. Furthermore, agricultural product exports have decreased relative to commercial export (World Bank, 2016). Given the sectoral fall in capital investment accompanying the previously indicated increase in security spending, this may be regarded as noteworthy.

4.2 Conflicts and the Threat to the Achievement of SDG 1 in Nigeria

Just as conflicts have undermined the achievement of the objective of MDG 1, it has contributed to slowing down the process of meeting the objective of SDG 1 and consequently poses a threat and portends its failure in similar ways. The trend of conflicts seems to have not only persisted but also worsened from 2015 when the MDGs elapsed and the SDG era started. Figure 4.7 presents pictorial evidence of this trend.

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Figure 4.7: Trends in the Fatality of Violent Conflicts in Nigeria 2000-2024

Source: ACLED (2024)

Figure 4.7 shows that there is little difference in the types of violence conflicts in Nigeria from 2000 to 2015, which was the MDG period, and from 2015 to 2024. In terms of fatalities, while there was a sharp drop in 2016, it continued to rise until 2024.

The country saw the Niger Delta conflicts persist and reinvigorate, the Boko Haram insurgency still at large, and the escalation of other long-standing conflict situations such as the herders-farmers conflicts, criminal violence and banditry, and secessionist agitations, particularly the notorious IPOB escalated into large-scale violence that have individually and collectively resulted in the loss of an alarming number of lives, destruction of enormous property, internal displacement of thousands of people, destruction of infrastructure, and the disruption of socioeconomic activities (EASO, 2021).

The emphasis here is that conflicts have engendered a plethora of conditions and processes that exacerbate poverty since the 2015 period when the SDGs were instituted, which is inimical to meeting the SDG 1 objective. These vary from the destruction of an alarming number of lives and property worth billions of Naira, internally displacing a relatively high number of the populace, disrupting economic activities to the disruption of education opportunities and processes of a large number of pupils and students as they drop out of school due to destruction of their schools, being kidnaping or the other. These factors have also contributed to the governance burden. The ways the above inhibit poverty alleviation, further create conditions for poverty, and particularly pose a threat to SDG 1 are enumerated and discussed in the succeeding section.

Destruction of Lives: Evidence indicates that violent conflicts have destroyed an alarming number of lives since the 2015 when the SDGs came into effect in 2015. The Nigeria Security Tracker (NST) database shows that there were a total of 6,274 instances of violence from January 2014 to Decemer 2019 Of these, 309 had to do with farmer-herder conflicts, which resulted in 3087 fatalities and accounted for roughly 5% of violent conflicts in Nigeria (Adigun, 2022). According to Nigeria Watch database, the clashes between farmers and herders lasted for 534 days (Adigun, 2022). See Figure 4.8.

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Figure 4.8: Incidence, Deaths, and Duration of Herders-Farmers Conflicts in Nigeria 2014-2019

Source: Adigun, (2022, pp. 7)

4.3 Lessons from MDG 1

In view of the performance of MDG 1 and the dynamics around it, as indicated by the empirical evidence presented in previous sections of this chapter, some lessons can be drawn. First, Nigeria failed to meet the objective of MDG 1 and conflicts played a significant role in this outcome. Violent conflicts immensely undermined livelihoods and led to a decrease in government earnings. Additionally, resources that would ordinarily be used for other productive sectors were diverted to fund the military and security. The lesson here is that for a government to effectively implement a development or poverty alleviation program or policy, inherent conflict situations must be taken into cognizance and addressed. This must be a priority component of the process. Another fundamental lesson is that the performance of MDG 1 was also dependent on the environment of its implementation. The Nigerian state’s environment was characterized by violent conflicts and was not amenable to the success of MDG 1. Negligence in addressing this factor and not incorporating it as a sacrosanct requirement for poverty eradication undermined the effectiveness of implementing MDG1, the failure to meet the objective. It can also be learned that the circumstances surrounding MDG 1 are factors that have long-term effect on society. Take for instance, the issue of disruption of the education of thousands of pupils and students which will leave a good number of the population uneducated and thereby lacking knowledge, skills, experience, and the capacity to create any meaningful livelihood. The impact will be enormous and long-term. Another notable example is the destruction of property and infrastructure. These will take time to rebuild even where the resources are available; talk less of Nigeria where adequate resources for development have always been a challenge. The loss of lives and the consequent dependents that have been dislodged from their sources of livelihood are also worth mentioning. More people have been thrown into the poverty net, and more burden has been created for the future. Emanating from all the foregoing is the crucial lesson that the failure of MDG 1 and particularly the impact of the violent conflicts has overlapping impacts that have created a greater challenge for the SDG 1. Worse still, the violent conflicts not only persist but are getting worse. This is why peacebuilding, conflict resolution, and mitigation must be priority components in pursuing the SDG 1.

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4.4 Discussion

The data presented and analyzed in the preceding section of this paper inform the achievement of the first research objective, which is to examine how conflicts undermined the achievement of MDG 1 in Nigeria. With empirical evidence, the study has indicated that in the MDG 1 implementation period, violent conflicts in Nigeria were responsible for the destruction of an alarming number of lives and property worth billions of Naira. The study also indicated that violent conflicts were responsible for the destruction of several social and economic infrastructure, disruption of economic activities, and destruction of the education of thousands of Nigerian pupils and students. Furthermore, the study demonstrated with empirical evidence that violent conflicts were responsible not only for a substantial decrease in government earnings but also for an increased government expenditure on military and security at the expense of other productive areas, such as agriculture, health, education, and investment. The foregoing impacted negatively on productivity, employment, and wealth creation and drastically harmed the livelihoods of a relatively high proportion of the Nigerian population.

This varies from previous studies, such as Ijere (2014), Oyeneye et al. (2014), Robinson and Anthony (2014), Onyeyekwere (2016), Lawal and Oluwatoyin (2017), Oluwatoyin (2017), Godbless et al. (2019), and Iyoriobhe and Ijie (2020), and others that focused generally on development policies and efforts in Nigeria and blamed their failure on deficit planning and implementation, bad government cum governance failure, corruption, and deficit economic system. It also varies from studies such as Ewetan and Urhie (2014), Onime (2018), and Ndubuisi-Okolo and Anigbuogu (2019) which focused on the role of conflicts and insecurity in the failure of development and poverty alleviation policies, but in a more general terms with no particular focus on MDG 1 SDG 1.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

The data presented and analyzed above confirm that the three specific objectives are achieved. As such, this study concludes that there is an inherent nexus between violent conflicts and poverty and that, conflicts played a significant role in the failure of MDG 1 as it undermined the livelihood of a good percentage of the Nigerian population. Second, the trend of violent conflicts persists and worsen in the SDG era. Violent conflicts continue to undermine the livelihoods of a relatively high percentage of the Nigerian population, posing a threat to the achievement of SDG 1. Third, it is learned that violent conflicts undermined the MDG 1 target in Nigeria, and addressing the country's conflicts is a requirement to meet the SDG 1. However, the sustained conflicts are yet to be mitigated and are compromising the chances of achieving SDG 1, putting its achievement at risk.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the study makes some recommendations, including the following:

1. The government and other development partners should adopt conflict resolution and peacebuilding as a sacrosanct element of any poverty reduction or alleviation policy or programme, particularly the SDG 1. This goes beyond merely addressing the situation of ongoing violent conflicts to addressing the root causes of conflicts in Nigeria.
2. Every factor essential to enhancing the livelihoods of the people should be prioritized in governance and pursued genuinely. This involves inter alia, education, health, agriculture and other vital sectors of the economy, employment generation, entrepreneurship, industrialization and security.

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3. Successive governments should endeavour to understudy the formulation, implementation, and performance of every previous development or poverty reduction policies or programs of the country as well as those of other countries, particularly the MDG 1 and draw lessons to form the foundation for pursuing any similar policy or program, particularly the SDG 1.

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